

The Mediation Role of Attitude toward Purchase in the Relationship between Country of Origin Image, Religiosity, Ethnocentrism, Animosity and Intentions to Purchase in the Egyptian Context

Sally Yassin¹, Prof. Dr. Ashraf Labeeb², Dr. Hazem Rasheed³

^{1,2,3}Arab Academy for Science, Technology and Maritime Transport, College of Business and Technology, Marketing department. /Alexandria/ Egypt.

ABSTRACT: This research investigates the relationship between differences (ethnocentrism, country of origin image, religiosity and animosity) which may affect intentions to purchase. In doing so, it measures the effect of country of origin image, religiosity, animosity and ethnocentrism and their relationships with intentions to purchase Chinese fashion products in Egypt, through attitude toward purchase. Both of positivism and quantitative approach represent an organized method of research that combine the deductive logic and the empirical observations of individual behavior together in order to be able to note a group of causal laws that can be used for general prediction patterns of human activity. This study collects the data of the required variable by making a questionnaire. This questionnaire targeted a population that is represented in customers who purchase Chinese fashion products in Egypt. The analysis conducted is applied using SPSS 22.0 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and AMOS 24. Due to the infinite number of the targeted population, the sample of the study consisted of 384 questionnaires gathered from Egyptian customers. The results of the analysis indicate that ethnocentrism and country of origin image have a positive impact on intentions to purchase and attitude toward purchase. While, religiosity and animosity have a negative impact on intentions to purchase and attitude toward purchase. Moreover, the results partially support the Mediation role of Attitude toward purchase in the relationship between (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Intentions to Purchase Chinese Fashion Products.

KEYWORDS: Attitude, Purchase, Origin, Image, Religiosity, Ethnocentrism, Animosity and Intentions, Egypt.

INTRODUCTION

During the past few years, the tendency towards the consumption of fashion products has increased tremendously worldwide as a globalization reason. Developed countries such as China, and United Kingdom have been increased their textile exports by increase personal protective equipment production (PPE) by 16.1% in 2020 reaching \$353bn. While developing countries such as Egypt have a significant remarkable increase in the imports of different types of products and raw materials from developed countries like China, and Vietnam (World Trade Statistical Review 2021). Crouch et al. (2020) described China as the second largest economy worldwide with 7.65% fastest growing GDP. China exports a great number of products and raw materials all over the world. Textiles and clothing are one of the sectors which China has a huge share of all over the world as (International Monetary Fund, 2020).

In 2020 the Egyptian ministry of commerce and industry reports through the general organization for import and export control, the statistics of imports in year as the following:

- Egyptian imports from China ranked first, with a value of \$11.570 billion.
- The United States of America ranked second, with a value of 4.577 billion dollars.
- As for the Federal Republic of Germany, it recorded third place, with a value of 3.959 billion dollars.
- Italy came in fourth place, with a value of 3.148 billion dollars.
- Then Turkey came to occupy the fifth place, with a value of 3.061 billion dollar.

From the previous research, the research finds that focusing in depth on the reasons which may affect the intention to purchase imported Chinese fashion products will be important to clarify part of the truth which may help the government in their economic policies. The main focus of the research is the intention to purchase which was indicated by (Peña-García et al., 2020) as a method of analyzing and forecasting customer behavior in terms of their interest in a certain brand and their desire to purchase it. Several factors were mentioned by (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1977) and scholars were examining these factors in different contexts and applications through the years. For example, Fakhmanesh and Miyandehi (2013) applied their study in Iran. The study was

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examining the effect of intentions to purchase foreign products, and they choose brand image ethnocentrism and animosity to apply their study.

This research investigates the relationship between differences (ethnocentrism, country of origin image, religiosity and animosity) which may affect intentions to purchase. In doing so, it measures the effect of country of origin image, religiosity, animosity and ethnocentrism and their relationships with intentions to purchase Chinese fashion products in Egypt, through attitude toward purchase. Through identifying these different factors and focusing on the parameters of measuring the relationships. This thesis provides some guidelines for Egyptian government marketing policies for the national fashion products. Traditionally, few researches focus on the effect of the intentions to purchase foreign fashion products and its sequences on the national fashion products. In addition, these intentions may affect in the long term the balance of payment of the country with a deficit due to the large number of imports versus exports and consumption versus production as reported in (Environmental Audit committee report, 2019).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Egypt being the heart of the Middle East with a huge potential growing economy. Consequently, it was a motive to develop a deeper understanding in an attempt to make a contribution in filling the gap in the literature of consumer perception of the imported Chinese fashion products from the perspective of Egyptian society in a certain critical time (during COVID-19 pandemic). The purpose of the current study is to examine some main effective variables in the influence of country of origin, religiosity, ethnocentrism, on consumer intentions to purchase imported Chinese fashion products, in Egypt. The study used structural equation modeling to measure latent or unobservable fashion constructs.

This study is going to examine the impact of (ethnocentrism, country of origin image, religiosity and animosity) in effecting the intentions to purchase imported fashion products from China based on two main reasons:

1. China came first in the list of Egypt's imports from the five largest countries in the world, and the volume of its exports to the local market recorded about 2.116 billion dollars, compared to 2.075 billion dollars in 2019/2020 (according to the central bank of Egypt).
2. Also, China, Hubei Province in Wuhan was the first human infection in the world with the Coronavirus (Covid-19), which is a 55-year-old man, which was discovered and reported on November 17, 2019 (according to the Chinese government announced in December 2019).

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In this section, the paper reviewed the theoretical background related to ethnocentrism, country of origin image, religiosity, animosity, intentions to purchase and attitude toward purchase.

Ethnocentrism Concept

The term consumer ethnocentrism was initiated in 1987 by Shimp and Sharma during a project aimed at empirical and conceptual analysis of consumer ethnocentrism. This term is considered as a socio-psychological phenomenon of ethnocentrism, and this term represents the agreement of members of society that their peers are always better and more noble than non-members. Consumer ethnocentrism measures consumers' personal attitude in identical ways across different domestic and foreign products (Renko, et al., 2012). Taking into consideration both the consumers' affiliation as well as their identity (Makanyeza and Toit, 2017). Highly ethnocentric consumers tend to buy local products more than foreign ones, according to the CETSCALE measure (Chrysochoidis et al., 2007; Netemeyer et al., 1991; Fernández-Ferrín et al., 2015).

Wanninayake and Chovancová (2012) describe ethnocentrism in words as "ethnocentrism" and highlight this phenomenon as the inflexibility of tolerating "both" culturally, while rejecting "the opposite" culturally. In light of this, the study suggests that by those definitions, a strong ethnocentric person can judge other groups in relation to the cultural dimensions of the language, behavior, customs, and religion of his or her group. The term 'ethnocentrism', as noted by Jiménez and San-Martin (2016) has been used primarily to provide appropriate explanations in relation to 'particular group behavior patterns and inter-group relationships', because it is a social event that refers to the propensity of certain distinct people. groups, the ideas perceived by the higher groups, and one's preference for choosing one's own things. In addition, Xin and Seo (2019) reported that consumers with a strong ethnic bias view the purchase of imported products as non-racial behavior that harms their economies and causes job losses, while consumers with a racial weakness view the benefits or value of products without regard to their origins.

Country of Origin Image Concept

In 1965, the term country-of-origin (COO) was discovered by Schooler. Country-of-origin (COO) has been defined as the image, reputation, and stereotypes that business and consumers attach to the products of a particular country (Nagashima, 1970). Schooler's study relied on evaluating consumers' attitudes towards services and foreign goods and proving that the country of origin of goods and products can affect their purchasing intentions of consumers, including the presence of some invisible barriers, and these barriers

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were represented in attitudes towards the people of any country. Martin and Eroglu (1993) further define the image of a country as the combination of all the descriptive, deductive, and informational beliefs one has about a particular country. Status image is defined by Kotler et al. (1994) as the sum of all those emotional and temporal characteristics that an individual possesses, such as engagement, convictions, ideas, memories, and impressions. Furthermore, COO is generally described by Usunier (2011); Vianelli and Marzano (2012); Kim et al. (2017); Xin and Seo, (2019) "Where are goods manufactured?". Not only that, but also, the product's COO has been described as the "country of production or assembly" by the manufacturer (Bilkey and Nes, 1982).

In addition, the labels "Made in" or "Manufactured in" indicate the country of origin (Nagashima, 1977). Many consumers, according to Degoma and Shetemam (2014), use country-of-origin words to rate items, whether a product is "better" or "worse", based on how they see the country, such as "Japanese electronics are trustworthy, German cars are great", and "Great Italian Food". A country of origin image, according to Jenes (2005), is "a unique form of image that includes a country's products, brands, companies, and more." The image of the country is created based on personal experiences and ideas about the country, as well as information obtained through many channels such as politics (domestic issues, international politics), telecommunications, entertainment (movies) and gossip. Guinness also states that the country's image consists of a variety of aspects, including national symbols, colors, clothing, traditional structures, artefacts, songs, literary works, characteristics of the political system, customs, and historical heritage, among others.

Religiosity Concept

Recently, terms such as religion and religiosity have appeared in contemporary literature frequently. Johnson et al. (2001) defined religiosity as the level of individuals' commitment to the religion they embrace and its teachings, such as the individual's attitudes and behaviors that reflect this commitment. Religiosity is described as a person's belief in God combined with a commitment to follow certain God-given ideals (Mortimer et.al 2020). In terms of religion, (Stark and Glock, 1968) defined religiosity as "a measure of the level of religious commitment that includes the rules and norms that adherents must adhere to." Religious commitment was also emphasized by (Worthington et al., 1988), who argued that religiosity includes the religious views and values of an individual. Previous literature has not been able to complete determinations about the strength of religiosity and how the effect of religiosity might influence the purpose of purchasing behavior or purchasing intent through exploratory the interceding part of attitudes towards Islamic, conservative ads and the subsequent attitude towards brands.

Nurhayati and Hendar (2019) make a proposal to measure the effect of religiosity on consumers' purchasing intentions. So did Mortimer et al. (2020) emphasizing the necessity of investigation in this field in order to generate and promote academic debate in this field. Based on the results, it was confirmed that consumers' religious beliefs have a significant impact on their purchasing intentions. The current literature strongly supports the attitude towards the purchase of imported fashion products and the purchase intent of the religious/non-religious person. Religiosity is characterized as the aspirational inner drive and love of religion which becomes the main drive of one's life (Allport, 1960). Not only that, but it is also an integral part of a religion that is manifested through positive associations with others and the fulfillment of various practical obligations/actions. Religiosity can be defined as a person's knowledge and beliefs about religious norms, sources of well-being, life gratification, struggles, and all other symbols of life. According to Damayanti (2018), religiosity is highly correlated with the benefits that are intended to be obtained for the specific benefits. According to research, there is a strong relationship between religiosity and life satisfaction.

Animosity Concept

Animosity is considered to be the remnants of hatred related to past or ongoing military, political, or economic events (Klein et al., 1998). So, for the first-time consumer animosity was introduced to highlight how negative consumer feelings and emotions towards another country can have a significant impact on product purchase intentions when dealing with merchandise from that country. The concept of animosity was first addressed by introducing the well-known animosity model of purchasing foreign products. The word "animosity" can be described as a relic of hostility associated with past or current military, political, or economic events. Consumer animosity has a negative impact on customers' thoughts and intentions because it reduces their desire to buy and consume foreign items as mentioned before (Antonetti et al., 2019). "Animosity is a hostile attitude that targets external national groups," states a study (Abraham and Reitman, 2018). As a result, consumers from emerging cultures may acquire a more antagonistic attitude toward national exogenous groups. Moreover, collective customers may perceive their identity to be intertwined with their national identity (Latif et al., 2019), and consumer animosity toward a country as a response to damage to national image (Huang et al., 2020).

In other words, Shoham et al. (2006) describes angry customers who do not alter or detract from the representation of target country products; Instead, they simply refuse to buy it. Another argument by scholars describing consumer sentiment is animosity of a particular country for historical or other reasons. The construction of animosity in four can be referred to as war, economic, political, social. Animosity differs from consumer ethnocentrism in that CETSCALE assesses public opinions about the purchase of foreign goods, while hostility is a country-specific concept. However, both concepts will have an impact on consumer purchasing behavior in the global economy (Li et al., 2012). Significance in terms of factors affecting consumer behavior in different countries Scholars

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have discovered that in order to compete successfully in international markets, firms must have a thorough understanding of the preferences and desires of different international consumers (Ettenson & Gaeth, 1991). However, with the entry of multinationals and the creation of new markets, different consumer behavior becomes a challenge, as multinationals will face cultures and nations that cannot be compared to the cultures in their home countries (Dwyer et al., 2005). Research on animosity has also contributed significantly to the international business literature that highlights the impact of negative influences of country of origin directly on purchase intentions (Hinck et al., 2004; Nijssen & Douglas, 2004; Klein & Ettensoe, 1999; Klein et al., 1998).

Attitude Toward Purchase Concept

Marketing research has always relied on the study of consumer attitudes, as attitudes are considered to be one of the most important determinants of consumers' behavioral intention in logical action theories. This is due to the logic that individuals' attitudes towards things represent their general assessments of their behavior (Sallam and Algamash, 2016). Situation was defined as the acquired tendency of individuals to respond either in a positive or negative manner on a continuous basis towards a specific object (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). Using the congruence principle, the relevant attitudes are those toward the performance of the behavior, and are measured with a similar degree of detail to that used in the evaluation of the behavior. It is an individual's internal evaluation of something, such as a branded product. Situation is defined as "a global and relatively continuous evaluation of an item, subject, person, or procedure (Hoyer and MacInnis, 1997)." This long-term interest stems from two primary factors. Additionally, Garg and Joshi (2018) describe the situation as the degree to which a person has a positive or unfavorable opinion of a particular behavior. It expresses a person's intentions for a particular product. The more positive the situation, the more likely the individual will engage in a particular behavior (Ajzen, 1991). According to the expected value model, the attitude to a particular activity is determined by the full set of available behavioral beliefs. As a result, attitude is a key element in describing human behavior (Ajzen, 1988). Several researches have confirmed that purchasing intent is positively and strongly correlated with the situation (Suki and Salleh, 2016). Attitude is a good predictor of a customer's behavior toward a product or service (Muposhi et al., 2018). Second, many theoretical models about attitude construction can be found in the social psychology literature, most notably in studies (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975), which have sparked interest in attitude research in marketing. In this crowded economy, nationalist sentiments increasingly influence consumer buying decisions (Cleveland et al., 2009). Marketers must first understand consumers' feelings regarding imported goods in order to resist the intense competition that characterizes today's markets (Dimofte et al., 2010; Riefler, 2012). Attitudes are described as "a brief assessment of a psychological component recorded in trait categories such as good – bad, harmful – useful, pleasant – unpleasant, and likable – unloved" in consumer behavior (Ajzen, 2001).

Intentions to Purchase Concept

Purchase intent is a method of analyzing and predicting customer behavior in terms of their interest in and desire to purchase a particular brand (Changa and Liub, 2009; Shah et al., 2012). Consumers with higher purchase intent are more likely to buy a product or service. In addition, the mental stage in the decision-making process at which a customer has actually acquired a willingness to act toward a product or brand is referred to as purchase intent (Wells et al., 2011; Dodds et al., 1991). An essential element of consumer behavior is his intent to buy, which is defined as the customer's desire to conduct a transaction with the seller in the literature. Buying intent of customers is very important to marketers because expected consumer behavior depends on it highly. Predicting consumer behavior is one of the most difficult challenges for any organization since it is always changing due to unknown and uncertain conditions, resulting in purchase intent that is difficult to assess under diverse circumstances (Yaakop et al., 2021). According to Kim et al. (2017), "purchasing intent" was a reflection of "the expected or planned future behaviors of consumers, or the likelihood that a belief and behavior will pass to purchasing behavior" (Kim et al, 2017). While, Rahman et al. (2017) mentioned that the intent to buy is a good indicator of the behavior while Ajzen and Madden (1986) mentioned that the intention variable plays an important role towards the behavior because the intention is considered as a mediator of the motivational factors that have an effect on the behavior. In the current literature, intent to buy in the context of imported goods, online shopping, and halal food has been described as (Khan and Azam, 2016). Social pressures from friends, family, and peer groups can sometimes reinforce an individual's purchase intent (Mukhtar and Butt, 2012). Furthermore, it was emphasized (Garg and Joshi, 2018, Mortimer et al., 2020, Yaakop et al., 2021) that purchasing intent is closely related to ethnocentrism, religiosity, attitude, animosity, and image of the country of origin.

EMPIRICAL STUDIES

In this section, literature is reviewed to develop hypotheses of the research for the effect of country of origin image, religiosity, animosity and ethnocentrism on intentions to purchase through attitude toward purchase.

The Relationship Between Ethnocentrism, Country of Origin Image, Religiosity, Animosity and Attitude Toward Purchase

ARSLANDERE and Yusuf (2020) searched in the effect of ethnocentrism on attitude toward purchase. The study sample group was determined through the appropriate sampling method, and individuals who were selected from Kerman province are preferred on a

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voluntary basis. The study included 335 participants (195 women (58%) and 140 men (42%)). The collected data were analyzed with the help of a statistically structured questionnaire using SmartPLS 3.0 software. The results found that there is a negative and significant effect of ethnocentrism on attitude toward purchase.

Thomas et al. (2020) made a study in the Indian market aimed to understand the effect of the ethnocentrism and attitude towards foreign brands on consumer purchase of automobiles. To measure the same, a survey consisting of a subjective questionnaire with a sample size of 108 was conducted. For the purpose of data analysis, exploratory factor analysis, CART technique and regression analysis were used in the study. The CART technique was used to develop a model that maintains ethnocentrism and attitude as a basis. This study showed that Ethnocentrism has a significant negative effect on attitude of people who have higher ethnocentrism and they are less favorable attitude towards foreign automobiles brands.

H₁: Ethnocentrism has a positive effect on attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products.

Wang et al. (2012) examined the effect of country of origin image on attitude toward purchase. The data was collected in five major cities from different geographic regions in China, such as Beijing, Shanghai, Qingdao, Shenyang and Wuhan. The research was conducted with consumers using a shopping mall interception technique, where shoppers were randomly contacted and asked to participate in the study. One major shopping center was selected from each of the five cities in China. In total, 1285 questionnaires were completed, however, 28 were excluded from the analysis largely because they were incomplete - leaving 1257 fully completed questionnaires, which were used for the final analysis. Consumers are more likely to make purchases that reflect their self-image and the image of the country. Because country products images are the primary criterion for purchasing and selecting unknown imported products, studies demonstrate that country product images have a highly impact on consumer purchase attitudes.

AYDIN et al. (2021) aimed to investigate individuals' attitudes toward the coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) vaccine and to explain the intent to vaccinate within the framework of reasonable action theory. The study extended the theory of logical action with the image variable of the country of origin. Study data were collected by survey method. The survey consisted of a total of 48 items, including individual innovation, subjective criteria, attitude toward a COVID-19 vaccine, intent to obtain a COVID-19 vaccine, image of country of origin, demographics, and general opinions about the vaccine and COVID-19. 333 participants answered the surveys. Data were analyzed by structural equation modeling using SPSS v.21 and AMOS v.23 software packages. The image of the country of origin is closely and positively correlated with both attitudes towards the German COVID-19 vaccine and the Chinese COVID-19 vaccine.

H₂: Country of origin image has a positive effect on attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products.

Alden et al. (2015) examined the effect of animosity on global brand attitudes. We collected data using online consumer panels, which resulted in samples with similar distributions of age, gender, and income. Samples consisted of 206 consumers in Brazil. Using non-student consumers, the authors tested the model in three diverse national markets ranging from emerging to developed: Brazil, South Korea, and Germany. The study supported the effect of animosity on global brand attitudes.

Abraham and Reitman (2018) explained the impact of animosity on attitudes toward purchase. This study used the mall intercept method to collect data from a sample of adult consumers in Tel Aviv, Israel. The questionnaire was translated and re-translated in style. Questionnaires were collected upon completion. The large number of passers-by and the mixing of individuals from all walks of life affected the choice of sites. A total of 264 respondents were recruited. 14 of the questionnaires collected were omitted due to incompleteness. Thus, 250 were valid for analysis. To check generalizability, the putative model was tested in two different contexts: Study 1 was conducted in Israel using the context of the Holocaust and Study 2 was conducted in Russia using the context of the recent political dispute with the USA. A convenient sample of Israeli Jewish consumers (n = 264) and Russians (n = 259) yielded a total of 523 questionnaires. In both contexts, the results of the SPSS and AMOS analyzes indicated a negative and significant relationship between consumer animosity and attitudes toward purchase.

H₃: Animosity image has a positive effect on attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products.

Mukhtar and Butt (2012) mainly focused on searching in the effect of religiosity on attitude toward purchase. A structured question is designed to elicit consumer attitude and the degree of religiosity between and within individuals. Data were collected from 180 adult respondents using the appropriate sampling method. Only 150 answers were considered appropriate for further analysis, yielding a response rate of 83 percent. Stepwise regression analysis was used to test the proposed model. After studied Muslims living in multi-religious societies who are considered more conscious about the permissibility (Halal) of products and it found that religiosity was positively related to attitude to purchase halal products.

Budiman (2012) clarified the relationship between religiosity and attitude toward purchase. The data collection technique used in this research was the sample survey technique using the questionnaire and the closed statement that uses the likeness scale and is given to the respondents. This research used the quantitative method and the respondents were identified using one of the non-probability sampling techniques, namely the purposive sampling. The criteria of the participants in this research were females who worked assuming that they had an income that supports their purchasing power and included decision makers towards bag products. Furthermore, of this population, the measurement of the research sample was 200 respondents. Results proved that religiosity had positive and significant effect on attitude.

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H₄: Religiosity has a positive effect on attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products.

The Relationship Between Ethnocentrism, Country of Origin Image, Religiosity, Animosity and Intentions to Purchase

Wu et al. (2010) defined ethnocentrism and its impact on intentions to purchase. A questionnaire was designed to collect the data contained in the study, which consisted of five sections. The data for this study were collected in Hefei city located in central China. Since middle school students are the leading consuming force in the future, their consumer propensity is significant in the near future. Two middle schools were selected and 600 questionnaires were submitted. 563 questionnaires were collected immediately and 504 questionnaires were considered valid for this research. The results show that there is a significant relationship between consumers' purchasing intention of domestic goods and ethnocentrism.

Kaur et al. (2019) identified the relationship between ethnocentrism and purchase intention in Malaysia. Related to the previous marketers recognize the importance of understanding consumer ethnocentrism in order to develop successful marketing and promotional strategies both locally `questionnaires were distributed but only 325 were valid for further analysis. The 75 invalid questionnaires were deemed unusable because they were incomplete. The questionnaires were distributed in the five malls around Kuala Lumpur for a period of two months. Data were analyzed using PLS-SEM technology. The results demonstrated a positive and significant relationship between ethnocentrism and purchase intention.

H₅: Ethnocentrism has a positive effect on intentions to purchase Chinese imported fashion.

Adenan et al. (2018) aimed to research the relationship between country-of-origin image and purchase intention. A self-administered questionnaire was distributed, and 225 completed and usable questionnaires were collected among East Malaysian consumers. Descriptive analysis, correlation analysis and regression analysis were used to test the data obtained from the obtained questionnaires. The COO effect is important in creating a positive consumer perception of the company's products, and ultimately influencing purchase intent. The result of this study shows that consumers in East Malaysia attach great importance to brand image and country of origin in highly engaged products because they are more involved in information search and decision making when purchasing these products.

Hien et al. (2020) focused on examining the effect of country-of-origin image on purchase intention. Data were collected through structured questionnaires distributed to clients in Ho Chi Minh City and Da Nang City using appropriate sampling method. Respondents were asked to select their respective electrical household appliances (eg, washing machine, refrigerator, air conditioner, etc.) with one specific brand for the selected product categories. Of the 352 questionnaires collected, 283 could be used for further analysis. The scale and hypotheses of the research model are then tested via SPSS 24.0 and AMOS 23.0. The findings which was applied in the electric household appliances in Vietnam, shows that the customer's intention to purchase is influenced by the COOI, implying that the COO plays a significant role in the process of purchase decision making. Customers' thoughts and perceptions of a brand are also shaped by the COO. The findings indicate consumers' trust in brands that originated in advanced economies (e.g. The United States, Japan, Korea, China). As a result, they are more popular and frequently chosen during the process of purchase decision making.

H₆: Country of origin image has a positive effect on intentions to purchase Chinese imported fashion.

Feng and Yu (2015) investigated the impact of animosity on purchase intention. A twofold experimental design was used in this study. Hypotheses were tested with a specific Japanese car brand among Chinese consumers. A total of 235 Chinese consumers aged 18–60 years participated voluntarily and a total of 199 of these had 235 usable responses. The analysis confirmed a strong interaction effect of consumer hostility on purchase intent.

Gupta and Singh (2019) examined the effect of animosity on purchase intention. To test the proposed hypothesis, the researcher conducted a survey using a structured questionnaire. Consumers of Chinese products are the target population of the study in Varanasi. 450 forms were filled out. After data purification, inconsistent responses were omitted from the study. 316 questionnaires were found suitable for the study and then were considered for the study. The scale was validated using confirmatory factor analysis. Then the proposed hypotheses were tested by structural equation modeling (SEM) using AMOS 20.0. Results illustrated that costumer animosity has a negative and significant impact on Indian consumers' purchasing intentions for Chinese goods.

H₇: Animosity has a positive effect on intentions to purchase Chinese imported fashion.

Quoquab et al. (2016) explained the impact of religiosity on purchase intention. A survey was conducted of 400 respondents in the Malaysian counterfeit market in China Town, Low Yat Plaza, and Pasar Malam as these are the most famous counterfeit shopping centers. The statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 21 was used for data analysis. Pearson correlation and multiple regression were used to test the research hypotheses. It was found that religiosity negatively affects behavioral intent to purchase counterfeit products.

Saputri (2021) investigated the effect of religiosity on purchase intention. The independent variables for the study were consumer ethnic centering, Islamic religiosity and consumer hostility, and the dependent variable was purchase intention. Data collection techniques using a questionnaire using the purposeful sampling method. The sample in this study was 150 respondents. The

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hypothesis was tested with the help of SPSS 22.00 for windows. The method used in this research is the quantitative method. The results of this study indicate that there is a positive and moral effect between Islamic religiosity and purchase intention.

H₈: Religiosity has a positive effect on intentions to purchase Chinese imported fashion.

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Haque et al. (2018) studied which was applied in Bangladeshi consumers purchase intentions toward foreign products by using religiosity, country of origin image, and ethnocentrism as indicators for purchase intention though the mediating role of attitude toward purchase. The survey method was used and primary data was collected from respondents by distributing hard copies of self-administered questionnaires as well as an online survey through Google Form to Muslim consumers in various locations in the cities of Kuala Lumpur, Johor and Penang. The rule for determining the sample size ranges from 30 to 500. Taking into account, 240 respondents were selected for this research and data were collected. Over a period of about 3 weeks. However, from 240 sets of responses, a total of 8 responses had to be discarded since then, either as missing data or not being returned. Therefore, a total of 232 answers were used for the purpose of analysis. The study contribution showed that there is a positive effect of country of origin and purchase intention through the mediating role of attitude. While religiosity and ethnocentrism showed a negative effect on purchase intentions through the mediating role of attitude toward purchase.

Wang et al. (2020) measured the relationship of religiosity and purchase intention toward green hotels in China through the mediator attitude toward purchase. An online Chinese-language online survey has been published online from October 1, 2018 to December 31, 2018 and from November 1, 2019 to December 1, 2019 on the following website. This free online platform is widely known among individuals, companies and organizations in China to collect raw data from online users. In this study, 404 respondents were collected, which exceeds the minimum sample size. A pilot test of 40 respondents was carried out to ensure the usability and validity of the developed tool and to prevent any problems that might affect the quality of the data obtained. The findings of the study indicate a revealed a major positive significant effect on intention for both religiosity and attitude toward purchase.

Furthermore, Aruan and Wirdania (2020), The purpose of the research was to investigate the extent to which religiosity influences consumer purchasing decisions when purchasing Muslim clothing. The research was conducted in Indonesia because it was the most populous Muslim country in the world. The subjects of the research were Muslim women dressed in Islamic clothing, both legal and illegal. 379 Muslim women participated in the survey. using the structural equation model. The research results of this study were differed from previous studies, as it was shown that there is a positive relationship between religiosity and purchase intentions, not only that but also, there is a positive relationship too between attitude toward purchase and purchase intentions.

H₉: Attitude toward Purchase has a positive impact on Intentions to Purchase Imported Chinese Fashion Products.

H₁₀: Attitude toward Purchase mediates the relationship between (country of origin image, religiosity, ethnocentrism, and animosity) and Intentions to Purchase.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter introduces the methodology of the research, in which the suitable methods are introduced that help in reaching the research aim, which is investigating the effect of (ethnocentrism, country of origin image, religiosity and animosity) on the intention to purchase Chinese fashion products through the mediating role of attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products. It is important to refer that this study is utilizing the positivism philosophy in order to achieve its aim. Positivism philosophy believes that there are two means could be adopted in order to understand the human behavior which are: observation and experiments (Arghode, 2012). This research depends on a deductive approach in order to reach its aim, deduction depends on quantitative data in order to measure the facts, which helps in reaching the results that have the ability to be generalized (Saunders and Lewis, 2012). Both of positivism and quantitative approach represent an organized method of research that combine the deductive logic and the empirical observations of individual behavior together in order to be able to note a group of causal laws that can be used for general prediction patterns of human activity (WYLLIE, 2019). This study collects the data of the required variable by making a questionnaire. This questionnaire targeted a population that is represented in customers who purchase Chinese fashion products in Egypt. Due to the infinite number of the targeted population, the sample of the study consisted of 500 questionnaires gathered from Egyptian customers. Only 420 had returned and after neglecting the questionnaires with invalid answers or missing data, the questionnaires remained to be analyzed was 384 with 100% response rate, where the sample is chosen to match 95% confidence level of (Saunders et al., 2016). Figure 1 represents the research framework.

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Figure 1: Research Framework

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

This section introduces the empirical study with the main findings and results after running the data analysis.

Descriptive Analysis of Respondents Profile

Table 1 represents the respondents’ profile for the whole sample that have participated in this study. In this section, the explanation about gender, income level, education level, and age are introduced with specific statistics obtained from the data collection approaches. In total, it shows that total sample participated in this research is N=384. It is observed that female respondent contributes the highest percentage with 57.7%. Further, the income level for the major of respondents is from 1000-3000 with 35.3%. Moreover, for the education level, the respondents who are participated in this study have Bachelor degree with 74%. On the other part, most of respondents participated in this research are age ranged between 32-40 years old with 39%.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Respondents Profile

Item	Category	Frequency (N=384)	Percent %
Gender	Female	221	57.7
	Male	163	42.3
Income	1000-3000	136	35.3
	3000-6000	128	33.2
	6000-9000	63	16.4
	9000 and above	58	15.1
Education Level	Bachelor degree	285	74.0
	High school	8	2.1
	Middle school	14	3.6
	Postgraduate	78	20.3
Age	20-31	138	35.8
	32-40	150	39.0
	41-50	61	15.8
	51-60	28	7.3
	61 and above	8	2.1

Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation for the research variables, as well as the frequencies of the research variables. It could be observed that the mean and the frequencies of most responses are in the agreement zone, as the mean values for the research

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variables; Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, Animosity, Religiosity, Attitude toward purchase, and Purchase intentions are 3.7532, 3.8338, 3.8883, 3.7481, 3.9636, and 3.9974 respectively.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis for the Research Variables

Research Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Frequency				
				1	2	3	4	5
Ethnocentrism	384	2.9195	.90212	0	148	142	70	24
Country of origin image	384	3.8338	.68724	0	15	82	238	49
Animosity	384	3.6519	.86205	0	55	67	218	44
Religiosity	384	3.7481	.67808	0	18	94	238	34
Attitude toward purchase	384	3.9636	.66827	0	0	93	212	79
Purchase intentions	384	3.9974	.45927	0	0	41	303	40

Data Testing using Validity and Reliability Analysis

The validity and reliability test of the research variables; Country of origin image, religiosity, ethnocentrism, animosity, attitude and intention to purchase Chinese fashion products. It could be noticed that the data showed Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (KMO) greater than 0.5, which was considered to be good. The average variance extracted (AVE) was found to be more than 50%. Also, all Cronbach's alpha values are greater than 0.7. The values obtained implies an adequate convergent validity as well as an adequate reliability.

Normality Testing for the Research Variables

In order to check the normality for the data, Table 3 shows the formal testing of normality assumption using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test of normality for the research variables. It could be observed that the research variables are not normally distributed, as the corresponding P-values are all less than 0.05.

Table 3: Formal Testing of Normality

Research Variables	Kolmogorov-Smirnova		
	Statistic	df	P-value
Ethnocentrism	.233	384	.000
Country of origin image	.341	384	.000
Animosity	.337	384	.000
Religiosity	.351	384	.000
Attitude toward purchase	.280	384	.000
Purchase intentions	.396	384	.000

As the formal test shows that the research variables are not exactly normally distributed, an informal test could be used to detect the approximate normality, which is called Rule of Thumb. It is called the informal test of normality, which claims that a variable is reasonably close to normal if its skewness and kurtosis values are between ± 1 (Kleinbaum, 1988). This rule could be applied only if the sample size is greater than 150. Table 4 shows the informal test of normality, where it could be shown that some of the skewness and kurtosis values are above the acceptance level of ± 1 , which means that the data under study are not normal. Consequently, non-parametric tests are used to describe the relationships between the research variables.

Table 4: Informal Testing of Normality

	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Ethnocentrism	.673	.124	-.421	.248
Country of origin image	-.498	.124	.541	.248
Animosity	-.612	.124	-.292	.248
Religiosity	-.549	.124	.509	.248
Attitude toward purchase	.041	.124	-.751	.248
Purchase intentions	-.010	.124	1.792	.248

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Testing Research Hypotheses

In this section, the hypotheses under study are tested using the correlation and the path analysis of the structural equation modeling. The Pearson correlation is used as the data under study are shown to be not normally distributed. The SEM testing is used as it is a neutral test and it does not require the normality distribution of the data under study.

Table 5 shows the SEM analysis for the impact of the (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Attitude Toward Purchase. It could be observed that:

- There is a significant impact of Ethnocentrism on Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Also, there is a negative impact of Ethnocentrism on Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding estimate is less than zero (Estimate = -0.138).
- There is a significant impact of Country of origin image on Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Also, there is a positive impact of Country of origin image on Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding estimate is greater than zero (Estimate = 0.250).
- There is a significant impact of Animosity on Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.004). Also, there is a negative impact of Animosity on Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding estimate is less than zero (Estimate = -0.095).
- There is a significant impact of Religiosity on Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Also, there is a positive impact of Religiosity on Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding estimate is greater than zero (Estimate = 0.425).

Furthermore, the R square is 0.435, which means 43.5% of the variation in Attitude toward purchase can be explained by the model.

Table 5: SEM Analysis of (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Attitude Toward Purchase

		Estimate	P	R ²
Attitude toward purchase	<--- Ethnocentrism	-.138	***	.453
Attitude toward purchase	<--- Country of origin image	.250	***	
Attitude toward purchase	<--- Animosity	-.095	.004	
Attitude toward purchase	<--- Religiosity	.425	***	

The model fit indices; CMIN/DF = 1.727, GFI = 0.909, CFI = 0.977, AGFI= 0.889, and RMSEA = 0.044 are all within their acceptable levels. The SEM model conducted for the effect of the (ethnocentrism, country of origin image, religiosity and animosity) and Attitude Toward Purchase is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: SEM for (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, Religiosity and Animosity) and Attitude Toward Purchase

Therefore, the first hypothesis “**There is a positive relationship between ethnocentrism and attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products.**” is fully supported. Also, the second hypothesis was: “**There is a positive relationship between**

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country of origin image and attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products.” is fully supported. In addition, hypothesis number third was: “There is a negative relationship between animosity and attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products.” is fully supported. Moreover, the fourth hypothesis was: “There is a negative relationship between religiosity and attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products.” is fully supported.

Table 6 shows the SEM analysis for the impact of the (country of origin image ethnocentrism religiosity and animosity) and Intentions to Purchase. It could be observed that:

- There is a significant impact of Ethnocentrism on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.022). Also, there is a negative impact of Ethnocentrism on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding estimate is less than zero (Estimate = -0.051).
- There is a significant impact of Country of origin image on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Also, there is a positive impact of Country of origin image on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding estimate is greater than zero (Estimate = 0.214).
- There is a significant impact of Animosity on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Also, there is a negative impact of Animosity on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding estimate is less than zero (Estimate = -0.093).
- There is a significant impact of Religiosity on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Also, there is a positive impact of Religiosity on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding estimate is greater than zero (Estimate = 0.207).

Furthermore, the R square is 0.447, which means 44.7% of the variation in Intentions to Purchase can be explained by the model.

Table 6: SEM Analysis of (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Intentions to Purchase

		Estimate	P	R2
Intentions to Purchase	<--- Ethnocentrism	-.051	.022	.447
Intentions to Purchase	<--- Country of origin image	.214	***	
Intentions to Purchase	<--- Animosity	-.093	***	
Intentions to Purchase	<--- Religiosity	.207	***	

The model fit indices; CMIN/DF = 1.677, GFI = 0.919, CFI = 0.979, AGFI= 0.900, and RMSEA = 0.042 are all within their acceptable levels. The SEM model conducted for the effect of the country of origin image, religiosity, ethnocentrism, and religiosity with the Intentions to Purchase Chinese fashion products will be illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: SEM for (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and intentions to purchase

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Therefore, the fifth hypothesis “**There is a positive relationship between ethnocentrism and intentions to purchase imported Chinese fashion products.**” is fully supported. Also, the sixth hypothesis was: “**There is a positive relationship between country of origin image and intentions to purchase imported Chinese fashion products.**” is fully supported. In addition, hypothesis number seventh was: “**There is a negative relationship between animosity and intentions to purchase imported Chinese fashion products.**” is fully supported. Moreover, the eighth hypothesis was: “**There is a negative relationship between religiosity and intentions to purchase imported Chinese fashion products.**” is fully supported.

Table 7 shows the SEM analysis of the mediation role of Attitude toward purchase between (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Intentions to Purchase. It could be observed that:

- Table 6 shows that there is a significant impact of Attitude toward purchase on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.004).
- From Table 6, there was a significant impact of Ethnocentrism on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.022). Moreover, Table 7 shows that the impact of Ethnocentrism on Attitude toward turned to be insignificant in the presence of Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding P-value is more than 0.05 (P-value = 0.123). Therefore, it could be claimed that Attitude toward purchase plays a fully mediation role between Ethnocentrism on Intentions to Purchase. (fully supported)
- From Table 6, there was a significant impact of Country of origin image on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Moreover, Table 7 shows that the impact of Country of origin image on Attitude toward purchase is still significant in the presence of Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Therefore, it could be claimed that Attitude toward purchase plays a partial mediation role between Country of origin image on Intentions to Purchase.
- From Table 6, there was a significant impact of Animosity on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Moreover, Table 7 shows that the impact of Animosity on Attitude toward purchase is still significant in the presence of Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Therefore, it could be claimed that Attitude toward purchase plays a partial mediation role between Animosity on Intentions to Purchase.
- From Table 6, there was a significant impact of Religiosity on Intentions to Purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Moreover, Table 7 shows that the impact of Religiosity on Attitude toward purchase is still significant in the presence of Attitude toward purchase, as the corresponding P-value is less than 0.05 (P-value = 0.000). Therefore, it could be claimed that Attitude toward purchase plays a partial mediation role between Religiosity on Intentions to Purchase.

Table 7: SEM Analysis for the mediation role of Attitude toward purchase between (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Intentions to Purchase

Dependent Variable		Independent Variable	Estimate	P
ATP	<---	ETHN	-.127	***
ATP	<---	COI	.272	***
ATP	<---	ANM	-.089	.005
ATP	<---	RELI	.391	***
PI	<---	ETHN	-.034	.123
PI	<---	COI	.182	***
PI	<---	ANM	-.081	***
PI	<---	RELI	.159	***
PI	<---	ATP	.123	.004

The model fit indices; CMIN/DF = 1.475, GFI = 0.917, CFI = 0.982, AGFI= 0.900, and RMSEA = 0.035 are all within their acceptable levels. The SEM model conducted for the mediation role of Attitude toward purchase between (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Intentions to Purchase is illustrated in Figure 4.

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Figure 4: SEM for mediation role of Attitude toward purchase between (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Intentions to Purchase

Therefore, the ninth hypothesis “There is a positive relationship between Attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products and Intentions to purchase Chinese fashion Products” is fully supported. Moreover, the tenth hypothesis “Attitude toward purchase mediates the relationship between (Ethnocentrism, Country of origin image, religiosity and Animosity) and Intentions to Purchase Chinese Fashion Products” is partially supported.

DISCUSSION

It is challenging to investigate the relationship between religion, culture, ethnocentrism, or even hostility against other countries and the influence on intention to acquire fashion goods from other countries. Fashion may provide a window into the social world, which is governed by an unspoken system of laws, practices, conventions, and rituals that govern face-to-face interaction. However, there is a scarcity of academic researchers studying the impact of religion, country of origin image, ethnocentrism, and enmity on fashion attitudes and perceptions, particularly among Egyptian customers. Given this gap in the research, the major goal of this study is to attempt to analyze the extent to which Egyptian consumers' religious, ethnicity, and what is the image of China as a place of origin for fashion items, and do Egyptian customers have any hatred towards China? That was the primary focus of this study.

The results of the research have demonstrated that country of origin image, and religiosity do carry a significant positive moderate effect on attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products in Egypt. Not only attitude but also, consumers' purchase intentions for imported Chinese fashion products. While ethnocentrism and animosity have indicated a poor negative relationship with attitude and imported Chinese fashion products purchase intentions. In Addition, attitude toward purchase played a role of mediator in the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Attitude toward purchase plays a fully mediation role between ethnocentrism on Intentions to Purchase. While it was partial mediation in the relationship of country of origin image, religiosity, and animosity and purchase intention.

The results of the research have demonstrated that country of origin image, and religiosity do carry a significant positive moderate effect on attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products in Egypt. Not only attitude but also, consumers' purchase intentions for imported Chinese fashion products. This result satisfies the research goals which were determine the relationship between country of origin image and intentions to purchase Chinese imported fashion through attitude as a mediator for the relationship. In addition, determine the relationship between religiosity and intentions to purchase Chinese imported fashion through attitude as a mediator for the relationship.

According to the results, the Egyptian customer has the financial power intentions and willingness to purchase Chinese fashion items. This trust is very certainly derived from prior years' experience with one or more Chinese fashion goods. Where the Egyptian customer is defined by religion, which promotes beauty, adornment, and perfume via the most exquisite clothing, fragrances, and

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fashion, and where the purchase purpose is a consequence of that religiosity. Which validated the veracity of prior research indicating a favorable correlation between nation of origin image and religiosity and purchase intention.

This research must have the impact and the value affecting the local producers in the manufacturing process, as they must search for the desires and needs of consumers and identify the most important motives associated with purchasing the foreign alternative. Is price competition, quality or modernity in designs the influencing factor in favoring the Egyptian consumer for Chinese fashion products? In addition, producers must try to adapt Chinese fashion products, which attract the admiration of the Egyptian consumer on the other hand, the government must try to return to using government mechanisms that urge support for national products in an attempt to advance the national product and increase local production.

CONCLUSION

This research had two major objectives. The first objective was to determine the relationship between (Country of origin image, Religiosity, Ethnocentrism, and Animosity) and Attitude toward purchase imported Chinese fashion products in Egypt. Hence, the current study investigated consumer intentions to purchase foreign fashion products. The researcher chose these types of products due to their wide popularity among consumers and for their rapid adoption in marketing on consumer behavior studies. This study was conducted by drawing a sample from consumers in the largest main cities in Egypt. The foreign fashion products industry in Egypt is one of the industries that have narrow studies in marketing. Driven by the high penetration of the largest economy countries such as China to the market and due to the harsh unstable economic conditions after the Arab spring revolutions, the export plan to Egypt was part of the portion of their exports plans aiming for a more effective and efficient impact on consumers demands and intentions to get new fashionable products. These fashion products have succeeded in attracting thousands of consumers to become 'fans' on these foreign products. After conducting survey with Egyptian costumers on the market, the researcher was able to conceptualize consumers' intentions to purchase foreign fashion products. The second objective of this thesis was to investigate the antecedents of consumer intentions to purchase Chinese fashion products. The study examined the role of attitude toward intention to purchase Chinese fashion products in Egypt. The questionnaire was distributing in the Egyptian market applied by stopping random people on the marketplace and asking consumers if they are buying Chinese fashion products and if they answered yes, the researcher asked them to answer the questionnaire in the Google Forms through mobile phones. It also discusses the theoretical and managerial implications for the future of the present study findings. The limits of present research, as well as suggestions for future research work, are discussed in the second part.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

The current study examined the impact of ethnocentrism, religiosity, country of origin image and animosity on intentions to purchase Chinese imported products in the Egyptian market with the mediating role of attitude toward purchase. As this study provided a statistically significant link between independents, dependent, and mediator variables. Marketers and academic scholars can use these findings to advance this discussion. This reasoning is provided based on purchasing of the Chinese imported fashion products. Governments, on the other hand, should concentrate on unofficially discouraging the importation of goods and services. Based on the findings and conclusions, it is reasonable to assume that religion, ethnocentrism, country of origin, and animosity plays an essential role in initiating and inciting purchase intentions among customers. As a result, international firms should consider religiosity, ethnocentrism, country of origin image, animosity while developing and marketing their products or services.

However, when we examined the prior literature, we discovered several gaps that had not been fully addressed. The majority of the literature focused on the current state of consumer animosity in specific countries while ignoring other critical issues. For example, standardization strategies may not be the best choice for companies operating in hostile countries, and such issues have not been thoroughly researched. Furthermore, entry modes should be a primary focus of research for companies interested in expanding into markets where there is animosity. A significant amount of research has been devoted to other sources of animosity, such as religious country image and ethnocentrism, which are related to animosity. ignoring the extreme influence that such elements may have on inciting animosity. Religion and country image are two major factors that contribute to nation diversification, and as long as such differences exist, conflict between nations will exist (Huntington, 1993).

In future study, it is suggested that the five aspects of religiosity be used. Beliefs, rituals, intellectuals, experiences, and consequences are examples of these aspects. This would give an extended model of religiosity, with the results yielding beneficial discoveries that practitioners might use as a guideline and researchers could use as food for thought.

While every attempt was made to ensure the study's neutrality, validity, and reliability, several limitations must be kept in mind while implementing the findings. These are described below:

1. Errors may have occurred during data collecting utilizing the survey approach. Although considerable effort was made to ensure that respondents understood the questionnaire statements exactly as the researcher intended them to be interpreted. Errors owing to misinterpretation or just incorrect data entry, on the other hand, cannot be totally out.

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2. This study was carried out utilizing convenience sampling, and while the sample region was limited to Alexandria and Cairo, as the two main big cities and as they are the most huge purchasing power in Egyptian governments as (General Mobilization and Statistics Agency statistics in 2020) more cities may have been added to improve the study.
3. Data was gathered in a limited period. The findings and conclusions are essentially only applicable to customer responses in three Northern Indian towns from November 2020 to March 2021. The findings do not indicate how these characteristics alter over time.

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Appendix (1): Research Variables Operational Definitions

Variables	Statements	Reference
Ethnocentrism	- It is unpatriotic to purchase imported Chinese fashion products.	(Xin and Seo, 2019)
	- Egyptian people should always buy fashion products made in Egypt.	
	- Curbs should be put on imports of fashion products made in countries other than Egypt.	
	- We should purchase products manufactured in Egypt instead of letting other countries get rich off us.	
	- Egyptians should not buy foreign products, because it hurts Egyptian business and causes unemployment.	
Country of origin image	- China is a technologically developed country.	(Yasin et al., 2007)
	- China is an economically developed country.	
	- China is a culturally developed country.	
	- China is good.	
	- China is reliable.	
	- China is friendly.	
	- I have a good feeling about China.	
Animosity	- I feel angry towards China involvement in the war against other countries.	(Ahmed et al., 2012)
	- I can still get angry over the China role in the other countries.	
	- I will never forgive the China for occupying and killing the civilians in other countries (ex: In first and second war/Japan).	
	- When doing business with the China one should be careful.	
	- China companies are not a reliable trading partners.	
	- China wants to gain economic power over Egypt.	
	- China companies often outsmart Egyptian companies in business deals.	
	- China has too much influence on the Egyptian and on the Egyptian economy.	
Religiosity	- I go to a mosque/church/ place of worship regularly.	(Wilkes et al., 1986)

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spiritual values are more important than material things. - If Egypt was more religious, it would have been a better country. - I consider myself to be very religious. 	
Attitude toward purchase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It's good to purchase imported Chinese fashion products. - I desire to purchase Chinese imported fashion products. - Chinese imported fashion products are pleasant. - Choosing Chinese imported fashion products is a wise decision. - Purchasing Chinese imported fashion products is a favorable thing for me. - Purchasing Chinese imported fashion products is a positive thing. - I prefer to purchase Chinese imported fashion products. 	(Chen and Tung, 2014)
Purchase intentions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am likely to purchase Chinese fashion products consistently. - I always want to purchase Chinese fashion consistently. - I am planning to purchase Chinese fashion consistently. - I will recommend the purchase of Chinese fashion to people around me. - I will actively talk about the benefits of Chinese fashion products to people around me. 	(Xin and Seo, 2019)